

IMPROVING THE PREVENTION OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY

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Abstract. The article provides examples from researchers' works on the guarantees of minors' constitutional rights, improving the prevention of juvenile delinquency and identifying the causes and conditions of offenses committed by them, and on adolescents with behavioral difficulties. Special attention is also paid to ideas for enhancing minors' knowledge.

Key words: Constitutional guarantee, juvenile delinquency, family relations, child-rearing, education and upbringing.

In the new Uzbekistan, ensuring the rights and freedoms of minors, protecting their legal interests, and most importantly, raising a harmoniously developed generation has been elevated to the level of state policy. The creation of a solid legal framework for protecting minors' interests is an important factor in implementing an effective social protection system and providing them with material and moral support. Currently, 40 percent of the country's population are minors. This figure alone indicates the urgency of the issue. In this process, great responsibility is placed on parents, mahallas, educational institutions, and the general public.

According to Article 77 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, parents and persons replacing them are obliged to support their children until they reach adulthood, to care for their upbringing, education, and healthy, full, and comprehensive development. The state and society ensure the maintenance, upbringing, education, and healthy, full, and comprehensive development of orphans and children deprived of parental care, and for this purpose encourage charitable activities[1].

In recent years, the number of offenses committed by minors in many countries of the world has been increasing day by day. Of course, the socio-economic, political, and ideological changes taking place in the world, as well as innovations in the spiritual and moral life of society, also have their influence on this. It is known that it is adolescents who are quickly and easily susceptible to both positive and negative influences. They especially want to show themselves and their abilities at a transitional age. If they cannot afford this at school or at home, they look for convenient conditions on the streets. Before you know it, joining criminal groups is quite possible. A teenager who commits an offense today grows up tomorrow. Analysis shows that two-thirds of recidivist criminals have already committed crimes in childhood.

This means that if we do not reduce the number of offenses among minors today, tomorrow the overall crime will increase. If we turn to the figures again, in recent years there has been an increase in the number of crimes committed by those aged 14-15 compared to those aged 16-17. This is alarming, of course. Adolescent criminal groups usually form around a certain leader. Often, the older of the members leads the gang. In most cases, such criminal

groups consist of teenagers living in the same area. Most of the group members disregard the rules, are prone to cruelty, some are addicted to smoking, alcohol, and even drugs.

The factors that cause minors to take the path of committing offenses are well known. However, we believe it would be beneficial to remind them once again. These include:

- unfavorable atmosphere in the family;
- material shortages;
- child abandonment, neglect;
- propaganda of violence, cruelty in the mass media, films;
- ineffective preventive work in educational institutions;
- meaningful organization of the minor's free time;
- an increase in drug addiction and alcoholism among adults.

As lawyer S.A. Vetskaya noted, the priority areas in this area are the timely identification and work with minors left without supervision and who have abandoned their homes, the identification of minors who commit offenses, persons who involve them in crimes and other antisocial acts, and the implementation of appropriate preventive work, as well as the prevention of organized juvenile delinquency[2].

Professor I. Ismailov emphasizes that the prevention of juvenile delinquency takes into account the specifics of their personality and those around them, the degree of their socially dangerous situation, the conditions of upbringing in the family, and the nature of the committed offense or antisocial behavior[3].

In our opinion, one of the most important characteristics of minors is independent thinking. This signifies the beginning of a new era in his intellectual activity. Any acts of behavior performed by them: antisocial behavior, inability to adapt manifest themselves as specific features of the transition period. Before committing the first offense, they may initially fall into the habit of leaving the house without questioning, not returning home, and not listening to the advice of parents and adults. At this very moment, extreme attention is required to the upbringing of adolescents. To understand why a teenager has embarked on the path of committing an offense, it is necessary, first of all, to analyze the social environment, conditions that surrounded him, and how they influenced the personality of the teenager. Internal psychological reasons, negative personality traits, i.e., unlawful behavior, the absence of firm life goals, a negative external environment, and poor upbringing in the family create favorable conditions for the formation of delinquent behavior.

The first stage in the formation of juvenile delinquency lies in the difficulty of upbringing. The social roots of difficulty in upbringing should be sought in the child's family and surrounding environment. Such a teenager often commits their actions under external influence. The change in his behavior depends on the change in the environment. In such a situation, it is important that educational institutions, the mahalla, and the general public, which are common subjects of crime prevention, have a timely positive impact on the adolescent.

Minors should be under the supervision and educational influence of their parents and educational institutions not only during lessons but also outside of classes. The analyzed positive results indicate that where pedagogical teams take on such responsibility and properly organize students' free time, where parents are not indifferent to their children's fate, violations of the law occur very rarely.

It is known that all individuals receive their first upbringing in the family and make their independent step into society through the family. If the family environment is healthy, the upbringing of minors raised there is properly organized, and their behavior and educational process are monitored. In such families, negative actions, such as antisocial behavior by parents and other family members, involving minors in various antisocial vices, are not committed. Because families of this category do not raise children who pose a danger to society. However, there are families in society whose negative consequences for the life of society are very difficult to imagine. Being outside the control of the family and educational institution creates a sense of recklessness among minors.

They conclude that no matter what they do, they will not be held responsible. In modern conditions of juvenile delinquency prevention, the main attention should be paid to the issues of early prevention, preventing offenses committed by them. Preventive measures carried out with adolescents are a factor that combines the influence of general educational, criminal, and legal measures. The main criterion for preventing offenses committed by minors is ensuring proper upbringing from an early age and timely correction of certain negative manifestations in a person, preventing possible offenses.

In this regard, in accordance with the Law "On the Prevention of Neglect and Offenses Among Minors," five main tasks for the prevention of neglect and offenses among minors are defined for the subjects. These are:

firstly, prevention of neglect, homelessness of minors, commission of offenses or other antisocial acts by them, identification and elimination of the causes and conditions contributing to them;

Secondly, ensuring the protection of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of minors;

thirdly, the formation of law-abiding behavior in minors;

fourth, socio-pedagogical rehabilitation of minors and families in socially dangerous situations;

Fifth, identifying and suppressing cases of involving minors in the commission of offenses or other antisocial acts.

In addition, this Law clearly defines the participation of parents or persons replacing parents in the prevention of neglect and delinquency among minors. In accordance with this: in order to ensure the safety, protection of life and health, prevention of neglect and offenses of parents or persons replacing parents, while fulfilling their obligations to support, educate and raise children:

firstly, not allow minors studying in educational institutions to be present during their studies in restaurants, cafes, bars, clubs, discos, cinemas, computer halls, premises equipped for the provision of Internet access services, or other entertainment (leisure) places, with the exception of being present in these institutions within the framework of educational activities or events held by the educational institution;

secondly, to prevent minors from consuming alcoholic beverages, narcotic drugs, psychotropic or other substances affecting intellectual and volitional activity, smoking;

Thirdly, take measures to prevent minors from committing offenses or other antisocial acts. Also, parents or persons substituting for parents take measures to prevent minors from being in restaurants, cafes, bars, clubs, discos, cinemas, computer halls, rooms equipped for providing Internet access services, or other entertainment (leisure) places at night without

the supervision of one of them[4]. We can see that the assignment of specific preventive tasks is aimed at preventing the main causes and conditions for the commission of offenses among minors.

Conducted research shows that the first stage in the formation of juvenile delinquency is characterized by a lack of proper upbringing. From a criminological point of view, this concept corresponds to such types of personality as immoral and partially offending personality.

A disadvantaged adolescent is a minor who needs correction and re-education. Their moral correction and upbringing are carried out in order to prevent this person from becoming a criminal, as well as to restore their normal relations with society, to form an active life position in them.

The behavior of each child with a difficult upbringing is unique; it is determined by objective and subjective factors of adolescent personality formation. This means that an individual approach should lead in educational and preventive work. The school should become a pedagogical center responsible for the life and behavior of children and adolescents[5].

Prevention of offenses committed by minors, by its content, is an intermediate link between general educational measures aimed at all minors and criminal-legal measures applied to persons who have committed offenses. All measures related to the prevention of juvenile delinquency should be aimed at the implementation of its main task - the cessation of personality disorders in behavior, the elimination of some of its negative characteristics, as well as the suppression of the influence of criminogenic factors of the microenvironment. Preventive measures should prevent adolescents with difficult upbringing from transitioning to more dangerous forms of antisocial behavior, ensure that they enter the right path in the future and take an active life position.

According to Eastern pedagogy, education cannot be separated from upbringing. The teacher should teach the student not only knowledge but also manners and humanity. However, this does not absolve parents of their responsibilities. Unfortunately, there are cases of parents or persons replacing them, who have forgotten their responsibility, evading or improperly fulfilling their obligations to provide for, educate, and raise dependent minors.

In conclusion, if we work effectively with representatives of various public and state organizations, mahalla activists to raise and educate minors as healthy and well-rounded individuals, create all conditions for them to engage in sports and physical education, and organize libraries for productive use of their free time, we will raise our children to be well-educated and highly spiritual. In addition, the systemic reforms being carried out in our country to prevent offenses serve to ensure the peace and tranquility of our people.

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